

INFRAEDI-02-2018

BioExcel-2 Project Number 823830

D4.1 – Dissemination and outreach plan

WP4: Dissemination and Training

Copyright© 2019-2021 The partners of the BioExcel Consortium

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Document Information

Deliverable Number	D4.1
Deliverable Name	Dissemination and Outreach Plan
Due Date	2019-05-30 (PM5)
Deliverable Lead	KTH
Authors	Michelle Mendonca (EMBL-EBI), Rossen Apostolov (KTH), Melissa Muscat (AL), Ian Harrow (IHC)
Keywords	Project Management
WP	WP4
Nature	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Final Version Date	2019-05-25
Reviewed by	Emiliano Ippoliti (Juelich), Richard Norman (NC), Gerrit Groenhof (JYU)
MGT Board Approval	2019-05-26

Document History

Partner	Date	Comments	Version
EMBL-EBI	2019-05-02	First draft	0.1
JUELICH	2019-05-07	Comments by Juelich	0.2
NC, JYU	2019-05-10	Comments by NC, JYU	0.3
KTH	2019-05-14	Version for PMB review	0.4
KTH	2019-05-25	Comments by PMB addressed	0.5

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the main objectives and direction of work for the center’s dissemination and outreach activities. It presents:

- brand redesign
- design and structure of the website
- selection of social media channels
- dissemination material such as brochures
- targeted events such as conferences and workshops
- communication with industry

The document also includes a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be monitored and presented in future reports.

Contents

1 INTRODUCTION.....	6
2 BRANDING.....	7
2.1 BioEXCEL LOGO.....	7
2.2 TEMPLATES FOR DIGITAL PRESENTATIONS.....	7
2.2.1 POWERPOINT PRESENTATIONS.....	7
2.2.2 PROMOTIONAL BROCHURES.....	8
2.3 PRINTED MATERIAL.....	10
2.3.1 FLYER.....	10
2.3.2 ROLL-UP.....	11
3 WEBSITE.....	11
4 NEWSLETTERS.....	11
5 SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS.....	12
6 PUBLICATIONS.....	13
7 EVENTS.....	15
7.1 CONFERENCES AND WORKSHOPS.....	15
7.2 WEBINARS.....	15
8 INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATIONS.....	15
9 INTERFACING WITH INDUSTRY.....	15
10 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs).....	16
11 APPENDIX.....	16

1 Introduction

A comprehensive dissemination and outreach plan is crucial to create awareness and maximise our reach by translating results from the project to the community. Establishing a brand is important as it increases value and promotes the organisation’s activities to the stakeholders. The overall dissemination strategy and outreach plan are set early in the project’s lifetime as reported in the current document.

A diverse set of communication measures will be put in place to promote the project and its results to the various target communities. Table 1 below lists the various communication measures and target groups.

Table 1. Communication measures and target groups.

Communication Measure	Target Groups
Website, promotional material (flyer, factsheet, posters)	General public, People interested in the overall goals and progress of the project
Press releases, Newsletters and social media	General public, People interested in the overall goals and progress of the project
Scientific publications	Scientific community, Industrial users
Whitepapers	Academic software developers/users, Industrial users, Industrial Software Vendors
Documentation and demonstrations	Academic software developers/users, Industrial users, Industrial Software Vendors
Invited presentations	Scientific Community, People interested in the overall goals and progress of the project
Webinars	Academic software developers, Industrial users, Industrial Software Vendors
Workshops and Tutorials	Scientific community, Industrial users

Presence at Events (booths, etc.)	Scientific and Industrial community
-----------------------------------	-------------------------------------

2 Branding

A distinct branding is required to define the center's identity in the community and media. The main branding elements are:

2.1 BioExcel logo

The BioExcel logo has been updated to a new version. The helix is now separated from the two adjacent letters "e" and "c" and they are now clearly visible. All new dissemination material such as flyers, business cards, powerpoint templates, website design etc. are using the new logo.

Fig 1. Updated BioExcel logo

2.2 Templates for digital presentations

We have updated the templates for the following material:

2.2.1 PowerPoint presentations

The new template was designed around a white background as opposed to the light grey of the previous template.

Excellence in Usability

- Make ICT technologies easier to use by biomolecular researchers, both in academia and industry
- Devise efficient workflow environments with associated data integration

3

Fig 2: Updated BioExcel presentation template

2.2.2 Promotional brochures

Brochures are created to reach our target audience and promote selected BioExcel events. Below is an example of a brochure designed for the 2019 BioExcel Summer School.

BIOEXCEL SUMMER SCHOOL ON BIOMOLECULAR SIMULATIONS

30 June - 5 July 2019

Science and Technology Park of Sardinia | Italy

Gain experience in biomolecular modeling and simulation tools!

The summer school will include lectures and hands-on sessions on:

- Molecular Dynamics simulations
- Biomolecular Docking
- QM/MM
- Free energy calculations
- Advanced sampling methods

Limited number of travel grants will be available.

Please apply online at

www.bioexcel.eu/summer19

Application deadline: 26 April 2019

Confirmed speakers

Alexandre Bonvin, University of Utrecht
Bert de Groot, Max Planck Institute
Vytautas Gapsys, Max Planck Institute
Giuliano Mallocci, University of Cagliari
Attilio Vittorio Vargiu, University of Utrecht

Contact: mmendonca@ebi.ac.uk

Organised by:

Supported by:

Fig 3: Poster designed for the BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations. (Note: The old BioExcel logo was used as the new version was under development)

2.3 Printed Material

2.3.1 Flyer

Flyers have been used extensively during various events as a standard way to advertise the centre to relevant audiences. Updated version of the flyer is available at <https://bioexcel.eu/about/press-kit/>.

The flyer is divided into two main sections: the top half and the bottom half, separated by an orange horizontal line. The top half features a central graphic of a molecular structure with orange and green spheres. The bottom half features a background of a DNA double helix with orange and green spheres.

Who are we?

Partners

- AcrossLimits
- Barcelona Supercomputing Center
- EMBL-EBI
- Ian Harrow Consulting
- IRB Barcelona
- Jülich Research Centre
- KTH Royal Institute of Technology
- Max Planck Society
- Norman Consulting
- Nostrum Biodiscovery
- The University of Edinburgh
- The University of Manchester
- University of Jyväskylä
- Utrecht University

Codes

- CP2K
- GROMACS
- HADDOCK
- MIMIC
- PMX

Workflows

- COMPSs
- CWL
- Galaxy
- KNIME
- Open PHACTS
- Taverna

Want to find out more?

WWW
<http://bioexcel.eu>

User Support Forum
<http://ask.bioexcel.eu>

Twitter
[@BioExcelCoE](https://twitter.com/BioExcelCoE)

LinkedIn
<http://www.linkedin.com/company/bioexcel>

YouTube
<http://goo.gl/5dBzmv>

...or join us for a beer at our favourite pub!

bioexcel
Centre of Excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research

A central hub for biomolecular modelling and simulations

Providing software, training and custom support

www.bioexcel.eu
[@BioExcelCoE](https://twitter.com/BioExcelCoE)

 BioExcel is funded by the European Union Horizon2020 program under grant agreements numbers 675728 and 823830.

What do we do?

- Develop widely used **software** for biomolecular modelling and simulations
- Improve the **performance** and extreme scaling (*exascale*) capabilities of the simulation engines
- Design **user-friendly workflows** for better productivity
- Provide **comprehensive support** to the computational life science community

Who is the centre for?

- Researchers** using computational modelling and simulation tools
- Developers** of biomolecular software
- Users and developers** of workflow systems
- Companies** (*pharma, chemical, biotech*) relying on simulations and computational modelling
- Cloud and HPC **infrastructure providers**

What do we offer?

- Training** courses for all abilities
- Webinars**
- Workshops**
- User Support Forum** (<http://ask.bioexcel.eu>)
- Knowledge Resource Centre** (including tutorials)

Commercial services

- KNIME nodes** of supported codes
- GUI workflows** - tailored solutions
- Site-visits** for in-depth expert consulting

[@BioExcelCoE](https://twitter.com/BioExcelCoE) www.bioexcel.eu

2.3.2 Roll-up

The current roll-up has been updated with the new logo and additional project funding information. Also available at <https://bioexcel.eu/about/press-kit/>.

3 Website

The main platform for outreach and promotion of the center is a website that can be accessed at www.bioexcel.eu.

A new website is currently being developed simultaneously whilst the current one is still online. The new website is based on the same core (Wordpress), but aims to be more user friendly by improving its overall functionality and design. It will achieve these goals by focusing on the streamlining of the website navigation tools and options which we believe to be the most important elements in a site's design. Users will be offered three unique viewing options which will include - *Funders*, *Industry* and *Academia*. Each viewing option will ensure only the most relevant information is offered to the appropriate user of that particular industry. The new design concept will take a more modern approach using high quality and futuristic images as well a simplistic colour scheme in harmony with the project's logo colours and overall identity.

Funders

Industry

Academic

Fig 4: BioExcel website with the new design concept showcasing 3 viewing options

4 Newsletters

The newsletters are an important marketing tool, which utilises the mailing list to keep existing members as well as connect with new prospects. The newsletters inform our readers about upcoming events, software updates, notable success stories, calls for participation in various activities, upcoming webinars etc. Newsletters are sent typically every month. According to the average email

D4.1 – Dissemination and Outreach Plan

campaign statistics by MailChimp (the leading company in the field), average open rate for industries is 20% and click rate is 2%. We have consistently achieved excellent rates of opening (30-40%) and click through (7-14%).

Below is a snapshot of the newsletter template:

BioExcel CoE Newsletter #17

Dear Rossen,

We have opened the registration for several key events that will be of great interest for many of you.

Drug Design and Free Energy workshop

If you are involved in drug design research and free energy calculations are an important part of your work, you may be familiar with the biennial [Alchemical Free Energy workshops](#) in the US. From this year, [BioExcel](#) starts reciprocal sister-events in Europe. The [first edition of the European chapter](#) will take place at the Max Planck Institute in Göttingen between 27-28 May, 2019. Many **notable speakers** and **pharma representatives** will get together for a two day workshop to discuss the advances in the area, various use cases, challenges and solutions. A highly recommended event for anyone doing Free Energy research work!

Molecular Dynamics (MD) Simulations

BioExcel is [bringing together for the second time](#) the **main developers** of some of the most popular and well-known applications for molecular modelling and simulations – **GROMACS, AMBER, NAMD** and **VMD**. The [2019 Seasonal School](#) will take place again at KTH in Stockholm between 10-13 June, 2019. It is funded and organized jointly with [PRACE](#), the main HPC resource provider in Europe. Over the 4 days of the event, the school program will allow participants to get a comprehensive understanding of the usage of the different codes; their scalability and performance, as well as ways to avoid potential issues; and learn the best practices about using them on HPC systems. Extensive hands-on sessions will cover more than half of time during the school. The event is one of a kind but you need to have experience with one or more of the codes. It's not for complete novices to MD. [Register here](#).

5 Social Media Channels

We are using the following channels to disseminate information about the activities and goals of the project:

- **LinkedIn** company page <https://www.linkedin.com/company/bioexcel-center-of-excellence-for-computational-biomolecular-research>
- **Twitter** account <https://twitter.com/BioExcelCoE>
- **YouTube** channel https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCd2hq8Q_ZyTU4YafEhweE5g

D4.1 – Dissemination and Outreach Plan

We have had success in disseminating our message through social media channels:

- The BioExcel Twitter account is the primary source of dissemination and has been quite successful so far. At the time of writing the account has 1220 followers and generates an average of 57K impressions per month. Below is an example of a successful tweet which reached a wide audience as depicted by the high number of impressions.

Top Tweet earned 8,849 impressions

How can free energy techniques make an impact in drug discovery applications? Join experts from **#pharma** and academia at the 2019 Alchemical Free Energy Workshop, 27-28 May to discuss success stories and challenges. Registrations close 24 March. **#drugdiscovery #industry #FreeEnergy** pic.twitter.com/fgHofnVTpN

← 1 ↻ 16 ❤ 33

- The BioExcel LinkedIn account currently has 200 followers and we will continue to grow this as the project continues.
- The BioExcel YouTube channel has 256 subscribers and we will attempt to test and implement short video formats to increase engagement.

The websites of the core partner institutions and external collaborators will also be used as publication platforms.

6 Publications

Research work published by partners will be submitted to peer-reviewed scientific journals, and will be one of the channels to reach more researchers and advance scientific understanding. Publication types will include:

D4.1 – Dissemination and Outreach Plan

- Journal articles
- White papers
- Conference proceedings
- Book chapters

Journals and conferences can be used as a pathway to target the scientific and industrial users. E.g. a recent publication titled 'A molecular mechanism for transthyretin amyloidogenesis' was published in Nature Communications which has an impact factor of 12.53, which indicates higher readership and citations.

The following journals and conferences have been often used by partners and will be considered for future publications:

Conferences

- European Conference on Computational Biology
- Large international (computational) structural biology conferences like, for example, the Biophysical Society meeting, various Keystone meetings, ELIXIR and INSTRUCT meetings, etc.

Journals

- Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology
- ACM Transactions on Architecture and Code Optimisation
- ACM Transactions on Computing Systems
- ACM Transactions on Parallel Computing
- IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems
- IEEE Transactions on Computers
- Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing
- Journal of Chemical Theoretical and Computation
- Journal of Computational Chemistry
- Bioinformatics
- Biochemistry
- SoftwareX
- Concurrency in Computation Practice and Experience
- Natures journals (i.e. not only Nature)
- PLoS/PLoS Computational Biology
- Structure
- Journal of Molecular Biology
- Briefings in Bioinformatics

Partners will ensure open access to publications either by self-archiving ('green' open access) via e.g. Zenodo or similar platforms; or open access ('gold' open access) via publishers who provide such and partnering with OpenAIRE where needed.

7 Events

In order to maintain consistency between our events, we have drafted event guidelines to be implemented across the project.

7.1 Conferences and workshops

Participation in conferences and workshops is one of the main vehicles to showcase our services and promote the CoE, which in turn assists in the further advancement of our outreach. Some of the main events that we will participate in are listed in section “Publications”.

7.2 Webinars

Online webinars are an efficient means to engage with users and deliver specific training to a large subset of our audience. The center will hold webinars on different aspects of the main codes and/or selected workflows. The first webinar in the new series is scheduled on 17th May 2019 on overview of GROMACS 2019 and its new features and capabilities.

8 International Collaborations

Establishment of relationships with related organizations is an important task for any international organization such as BioExcel. It leverages the shared expertise, infrastructure, resources and network to provide joint benefits of e.g. co-development, training, outreach, policy matters.

In the first phase of BioExcel we have established formal partnerships with the international initiatives ELIXIR, INSTRUCT, MolSSI, HPC-Europa3, MuG VRE, Vi-SEEM, and Open PHACTS, as well as national leaders such as Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU) and Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS) (<https://bioexcel.eu/collaborations>). In addition, we will continue building on the following existing, or establish future, collaborations that we consider of high importance for centre operations:

- Infrastructure providers – PRACE, EOSC, EUDAT, EGI
- Research clusters – EOSC-Life, IMIs
- Training networks – CORBEL, RITrain, LifeTrain
- Other CoEs – FocusCoE, MaX, POP, CompBioMed
- National and global initiatives - Software Sustainability Institute (SSI), CCPBioSim, GA4GH, CWL
- US organizations - FDA, NIH Data Commons, NSF, Oak Ridge Laboratory
- International alliances - Pistoia Alliance, CEFIC, FoodDrinkEurope
- Policy activities – ETP4HPC, EXDCI-2

9 Interfacing with industry

D4.1 – Dissemination and Outreach Plan

Molecular modellers working in Life Science industry such as biopharmaceuticals R&D and Biotech SMEs are an important community of users for our core software codes, especially GROMACS, PMX and HADDOCK. We already have a network of user contacts in numerous pharma companies including AstraZeneca, UCB and Janssen, who are also represented on our Industry Advisory Board. Besides conferences and workshops attended by life science industry, we maintain strong collaborative relationships through a series of site visits and focus group meetings. We are also planning to implement more industry relevant content on the BioExcel website. More details on industry engagement will be disclosed in future deliverables for user support from WP3 (e.g. use cases) and WP5 (e.g. business plans).

Outreach towards industry will be enforced by leveraging on existing networks. In particular, FocusCoE provides services for industry outreach; ELIXIR and EMBL-EBI's run active SME Forums and have strong networks.

10 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Table 2 below lists the set of KPIs, which will be monitored in the dissemination activities and reported in subsequent reports:

Table 2. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPI	Reachable target	Stretch target
Social media - Twitter	75 tweets per quarter	120 tweets per quarter
Number of new Twitter followers	90 new followers per quarter	150 new followers per quarter
Social media - LinkedIn	24 updates per quarter	45 updates per quarter
Number of website visits	3300 per month	4500 per quarter
Number of people subscribed to the general BioExcel mailing list (potentially to be renamed to "Join BioExcel")	30	45

11 Appendix

BioExcel-2 Dissemination & Event Guidelines

D4.1 – Dissemination and Outreach Plan

The document below outlines the BioExcel dissemination and event guidelines. It is curated by WP4 but it is meant to be a living document, suggestions can be added by anyone in the CoE. The aim is to provide useful information about the available communication channels, standard working practice and tips & tricks.

BioExcel Dissemination channels

Below is a list of the BioExcel dissemination channels and which consortium member you can contact to add content to the channel. If you would like to help manage a specific channel please contact Michelle Mendonca so that we can give you direct access.

- **Twitter** - <https://twitter.com/bioexcelcoe>
 - You can forward what you want to advertise or request a retweet if you tweeted from your own account.
 - All BioExcel-sponsored events need to be tweeted with the BioExcel website link. Refer website (section 3) for more information
 - Use image or gif
 - Recommendation: include no more than 2-3 relevant hashtags
 - Use @ to tag people to your message

- Consider creating short and meeting-specific hashtags to generate engagement.

Contact : Michelle Mendonca

- **LinkedIn**
 - All BioExcel-sponsored events need to be posted with the BioExcel website link. Refer website (section 3) for more information
 - Add updates on events, webinars, blog posts, etc. with short text and a link
 - Add yourself as a BioExcel employee by adding a new position in your profile (Experience section), search for BioExcel under company. You will automatically be added as employee on the BioExcel company page.

Contact : Michelle Mendonca

- **Website**
 - BioExcel-sponsored events will be added to the events page or a new post will be created if needed.
 - To create an event/add content or learn about the interface, contact Michelle.

D4.1 – Dissemination and Outreach Plan

- Consider writing a blog post about your work/new release. Let Michelle & Vera know so we can publicize the blog post

Contact : Michelle Mendonca

- **BioExcel Mailing list**

- Ideally an update should be part of the BioExcel newsletter

Contact : Rossen Apostolov or Michelle Mendonca

Images

Using images with your social media updates is a very effective way to increase the engagement rate (applicable to all platforms).

Please be mindful that you need to check if the license of an image allows you to share the image on social media/websites. If in doubt, please check with Michelle & Vera.

Webinar dissemination

Checklist for Webinar Advertising Campaign

1. Current webinar includes last slide to advertise the next webinar
2. Three weeks prior to webinar date send email to invite registration
3. Two weeks prior to webinar disseminate publicity via email to networks
4. One week prior to webinar date send reminder to registrants
5. One week prior to webinar send email to invite registration
6. One day prior to webinar date send reminder to registrants

Event guidelines

The list below is meant to give you ideas and point you to helpful resources. It also points out where we have BioExcel templates that we would like you to use

Training event

Pre-course preparation

- Define learning outcomes for the course
- Define objectives for the course
- Clearly defined audience for the workshop, including any prerequisites
- As a guideline try and open the registration event up to 6 months before the date (programme can be in draft with fixed beginning and end times); register interest list can be implemented at an earlier stage.

Programme

D4.1 – Dissemination and Outreach Plan

- Address course expectations at the beginning of the course. Ideally with time allocated to introductions. This could be in group if you have lots of people attending.
- Gamestorming has useful activities that can be used to capture participants expectations and icebreakers
- Reserve time to fill in the feedback form and a wrap-up/conclusion session at the end
- If possible try and mix hands-on and lecture rather than big blocks (not always possible)
- People's attention span is short
- Add sufficient time for breaks to the programme, besides allowing the participants to network, it also gives you a time buffer if a session overruns.
- If budget allows, add a socialising event e.g. dinner, excursion, reception etc.
- Consider using a [Slack channel](#), Gitter, or twitter hashtag to encourage community building
- Consider gender balance when putting your speaker list together

Branding

- For all BioExcel-sponsored events, a clear logo with the tagline should be included. These can be found on our website. <https://bioexcel.eu/about/press-kit/>

Post-event

- Post-course survey should be filled in during the event
- Contact Vera Matser for the surveymonkey template, please use the template as WP4 KPIs are dependent on the questions.
- De-brief with trainers and organisers to discuss participant feedbacks and their own impressions of the course
- Define improvements for the next iteration if applicable
- Post 6 months and 2 years survey to ascertain long-term feedback
- Done by WP4 as part of quality assessment & impact